

Random Forest-Based Soil Moisture Downscaling in Southeastern Hungary

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Abstract: Soil moisture is a key variable in the water and energy cycle and has an important role in agricultural drought monitoring. Existing remote sensing products, such as SMAP, are limited in their regional applicability due to coarse spatial resolution. To overcome this, downscaling techniques are widely used. Machine learning methods, especially Random Forest, have shown strong potential for integrating multi-sensor auxiliary data to retrieve high-resolution soil moisture. In this study, NASA's SMAP Level-3 Enhanced product at 9 km resolution was captured via Google Earth Engine. Auxiliary predictor variables, including Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter coefficients (VV and VH polarizations), MODIS-derived vegetation indices (NDVI and EVI), and land surface temperature, were incorporated. Monthly datasets from April to October for 2021 and 2022 were used over south-eastern Hungary to compare normal conditions and the drought-affected 2022 growing season. Random Forest models were trained to establish statistical relationships with SMAP soil moisture and applied to produce 1 km downscaled maps. The model showed strong performance, consistent with original SMAP retrievals, while capturing the spatial heterogeneity of drought conditions. Validation against ground-based measurements revealed uncertainties arising from the depth mismatch between SMAP's 0–5 cm sensing depth and in-situ observations collected at 10 cm, which may be particularly pronounced during drought conditions.

Keywords: soil moisture; SMAP; downscaling; remote sensing; Random Forest.

1 Introduction

Soil moisture (SM) is a key component of the terrestrial water and energy cycle and is one of the main sources of available water for plants, especially capillary water, and is a critical factor affecting crop growth (Bai et al. 2019, Dobriyal et al. 2012). So, accurate estimation of SM dynamics is essential for improving water resource management and assessing drought effects in agricultural regions.

Nowadays, satellite remote sensing has enabled large-scale monitoring of soil moisture, with the Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) mission providing reliable observations at high temporal frequency (Liu et al. 2019, Mohanty et al. 2017). However, the relatively coarse spatial resolution of SMAP products (e.g., 9 km or 36km) limits their capability for field-scale analysis in heterogeneous agricultural regions (Li et al. 2018, Sun and Cui 2021).

To overcome this limitation, downscaling approaches have been developed by integrating higher-resolution auxiliary data such as synthetic aperture radar (SAR), vegetation

indices (VIs), and land surface temperature (LST) (Lievens et al. 2017, Santi et al. 2018). In particular, the integration of Sentinel-1 SAR data with SMAP observations has shown strong potential for improving soil moisture estimation at finer spatial scales (Das et al. 2019, Meyer et al. 2022). Machine learning methods, such as Random Forest (RF), have shown strong capability in capturing nonlinear relationships between soil moisture and environmental variables (Breiman 2001, Zhao et al. 2018).

Despite these advances, region-specific evaluations remain limited, especially under extreme climatic conditions. Central and Eastern Europe, including Hungary, experienced severe drought during the 2022 growing season (Bevacqua et al. 2024), highlighting the need for high-resolution soil moisture data.

Therefore, this study aims to develop a Random Forest-based downscaling approach to estimate soil moisture at 1-km resolution from SMAP data, using Sentinel-1 SAR, MODIS vegetation indices, and land surface temperature. The method is applied in Southeastern Hungary for the 2021–2022 growing seasons to evaluate its performance in capturing spatial variability and drought conditions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study Area

This research was conducted in Békés County, located in the south-eastern part of the Great Hungarian Plains (Alföld), between 46.2°N and 47.2°N latitude and 20.4°E and 21.8°E longitude, covering approximately 5,600 km² (Figure 1). The area is predominantly flat, with elevations ranging from 80 to 100 meters above sea level. The region has a continental climate, featuring warm, dry summers and cold winters. In recent years, the region has experienced increasing drought, particularly in summer, due to high temperatures and evapotranspiration rates, and intensifying SM deficits (Kis et al. 2025). This continuous moisture deficit makes the area highly sensitive to agricultural drought.

2.2 Datasets

Soil moisture and auxiliary datasets were used to develop the downscaling model. Surface soil moisture data were obtained from the SMAP Level-3 Enhanced passive product (SPL3SMP_E), which provides global estimates at ~9 km spatial resolution representing the top 0–5 cm soil layer (O'Neill et al. 2023). Sentinel-1 SAR data (GRD) were used as primary predictors due to their sensitivity to surface moisture conditions, including VV and VH backscatter coefficients (Huang et al. 2019). Additionally, MODIS (moderate-resolution imaging spectroradiometer)

Figure 1. Study area.

products were incorporated to account for vegetation and thermal effects, including NDVI and EVI from MOD13A1, and land surface temperature (LST) from MOD11A2. The formulas are as follows:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED} \quad (1)$$

$$EVI = 2.5 \times \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+6 \times RED - 7.5 \times BLUE + 1} \quad (2)$$

RED, NIR, and BLUE refer to MODIS bands. The summary of the data sources is presented in Table 1. Additionally, four in situ SM station measurements (Békés, Szeghalom, Nagybanhegy, and Battonya) at a depth of 10 cm were collected from the OVF database and used to validate the downscaled soil moisture estimates.

These datasets provide complementary information on vegetation dynamics and surface energy balance, which are closely linked to soil moisture variability (Beck et al. 2021, Nadeem et al. 2022).

2.3 Methodology

First, the downscaling methodology involved preprocessing and harmonization in both the temporal and spatial domains. We calculated monthly averages for the growing season, from April to October 2021 to 2022, to reduce noise and maintain consistent timing. Soil moisture data from SMAP with 9 km resolution were the target variable, while Sentinel-1 (VV, VH) and MODIS-derived variables (NDVI, EVI, LST) were used as predictors. To capture the non-linear relationship between SMAP soil moisture and the predictor variables, a Random Forest (RF) regression model was employed. The dataset was then split into 80% for training and 20% for testing. We

Table 1. Summary of datasets used in this study.

Data Source	Variable(s)	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution
SMAP (SPL3SMP_E)	Surface soil moisture (0–5 cm)	9 km	Daily
Sentinel-1 SAR	Backscatter (VV, VH)	10 m	6–12 days
MOD13A1	NDVI, EVI	500 m	16-day
MOD11A2	LST	1 km	Daily

optimized the RF model by performing a grid search and using 5-fold cross-validation. The model used SMAP soil moisture as the dependent variable and Sentinel-1 (VV, VH) and MODIS variables (NDVI, EVI, LST) as inputs, as in formula 1:

$$SM_{SMAP} = f_{RF}(VV_i, VH_i, NDVI_i, EVI_i, LST_i) \quad (1)$$

To improve prediction stability and reduce overfitting, RF hyperparameters were optimized. To ensure spatial consistency, all predictor variables were aggregated to the SMAP resolution (9 km) during model training. After the model was developed, it was applied to higher-resolution predictor datasets to generate soil moisture estimates at 1 km resolution. Quality control procedures were implemented to remove unreliable observations, including SAR noise and pixels affected by clouds. We used the Google Earth Engine (GEE) Python API in Google Colab to process the data.

3 Results

3.1 Model Performance

The RF model showed satisfactory performance in predicting soil moisture during the 2021–2022 growing season. The optimized model achieved a coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.74$) on the test dataset, with a root mean square error (RMSE = 0.021).

These results indicate that the selected predictors—Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter (VV, VH), MODIS vegetation indices (NDVI, EVI), and land surface temperature (LST)—can capture the spatial and temporal variability of soil moisture at coarse resolution. In Figure 2, the feature-importance ranking and the SHAP analysis are presented. The SHAP values showed that LST was the most influential predictor, with higher values generally contributing negatively to SM estimates. Vegetation indices (NDVI and EVI) exhibited moderate importance, while SAR backscatter variables (VV and VH) had relatively smaller contributions. Overall, the model captured the expected relationships between soil moisture and environmental variables.

3.2 Downscale Analysis

A visual comparison of the monthly mean SM between the original 9km SM and the model downscaled to 1 km is presented in Figure 3 for April–October 2022. The downscaled results preserve the overall spatial patterns observed in SMAP, while providing finer spatial detail and improved representation of local variability. Lower soil moisture values are evident during June and July, reflecting the dry conditions of the 2022 growing season.

The monthly time series comparison between the downscaled SMAP and four in situ stations is shown in

Figure 2. SHAP feature importance of the Random Forest model.

Figure 3. Comparison of the monthly mean Original and downscale SMAP.

Figure 4. Both datasets followed the same temporal pattern, and the average correlation coefficient between in-situ data and downscaled data was 0.68. However, the in-situ data were captured at a depth of 10 cm, whereas the SMAP downscaled estimate is at a depth of 5cm, which is causing uncertainty.

Figure 4. Time series of downscaled SM product and in-situ data.

4 Discussion

The RF model showed strong performance ($R^2=0.74$), indicating an acceptable and accurate estimation of SM from multi-source remote sensing data. This result aligns with previous studies on SMAP SM downscaling, in which RF achieved high accuracy ($R^2=0.84$) by integrating multiple predictors (Mao et al. 2022). Among the feature importance metrics, LST was the primary downscaling factor during the growing season, reflecting its significant impact on evapotranspiration. Similar findings were reported in a study on the Loess Plateau, where LST had the most significant impact on surface processes, including vegetation growth during high-temperature periods (Wang et al. 2024). In another study, a thermal inertia-based downscaling approach that integrates land surface temperature and vegetation information has been proposed, emphasizing the important role of temperature-

related variables in capturing soil moisture variability (Fang et al. 2022). For further model performance improvement, in future studies, more predictors such as topographic variables and soil properties should be considered. Moreover, this downscaling model relies on a monthly downscaling framework, which reduces noise and ensures

robust representation of SM dynamics. Although daily downscaled products are available (e.g., Lakshmi and Fang, 2023), the monthly framework is particularly suitable for drought monitoring and seasonal-scale analysis. Extending the study period could reduce its uncertainty and improve the model.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this study explored the capability of a random forest-based machine learning method for soil moisture downscaling using MODIS products and SAR data across southeastern Hungary. SMAP data at 9 km resolution were downscaled to 1 km resolution. The results demonstrated improved spatial information on SM distribution, and the downscaled SM provides finer details useful for local-level studies, such as early drought detection in agricultural regions.

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6 References

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